

Electrochemical Conversion of Furnace
exhaust gas to Ethanol for sustainable
steel making

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Abstract

Electrochemical conversion of waste gases devoid of their calorific value to useful chemicals offers one means to address the ever-depleting reserves of conventional fuels. On the other hand, it also brings forth a possible solution to the emission of greenhouse gas problem faced by industries today. Switching over to greener and conventional sources of energy has been accepted as a solution for many modern small-scale industries. However, these leaves out major production houses in the Iron and Steel sector with a tough choice. Using hydrogen for steel making^[1] entails a humongous expense of changing conventional steelmaking machines like Blast furnace, LD Convertors, Cupolas. Here we present an efficient method to re-use the exhaust gas from blast furnace for preparing useful chemicals such as Ethanol which has many fold uses even as fuel. Thus, we aim to achieve the goal of Waste to Energy. We have demonstrated efficient conversion of furnace gas to ethanol by simulating blast furnace conditions in a laboratory tube furnace. The process has been made efficient by involving Arduino based robotic circuitry to keep record of chemical yield of the furnace as well as the cell. Real time monitoring as well as data collection has enabled us to gain more familiarity of the system. Here, we propose a self-learning program to mitigate fluctuations in the blast furnace as well as send constant feedback to the operator so as to maintain the optimum conversion efficiency. This is a minute step towards a fully automatic system for Exhaust -CO₂ conversion which has enough merit to solve the emission problem in most steel industries. Having stated the goal for our project we have showed enough evidence to claim the plausibility of our model system. The report also contains a list of experiments and simulations which are necessary and may be carried out later in our continuing work.

1.0 Introduction

1.1 Background.

Carbon dioxide occurs naturally in the atmosphere and is about 0.04% of all the gases. It is an essential compound for photosynthesis of plants for their food and energy. However CO₂ has very few other uses that are beneficial to humankind. Carbon dioxide contributes to air pollution as a greenhouse gas. Carbon dioxide^[2] traps solar radiation at a ground level creating ground-level ozone . The earth's atmosphere is designed to keep life warm at night which results in warming of ocean waters. Oceans has the ability to absorb carbon dioxide from the atmosphere. However, with increasing temperature this ability founders.

1.2 Climate change: On Earth, human activities are changing the natural greenhouse. Over the last century the burning of fossil fuels like coal and oil has increased the concentration of atmospheric carbon dioxide (CO₂). This happens because the coal or oil burning process combines carbon with oxygen in the air to make CO₂. To a lesser extent, the clearing of land for agriculture, industry, and other human activities has increased concentrations of greenhouse gases^[3].

In its Fifth Assessment Report, the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, a group of 1,300 independent scientific experts from countries all over the world under the auspices of the United Nations, concluded there's a more than 95 percent probability that human activities over the past 50 years have warmed our planet.

The industrial activities that our modern civilization depends upon have raised atmospheric carbon dioxide levels from 280 parts per million to 412 parts per million in the last 150 years. The panel also concluded there's a better than 95 percent probability that human-produced greenhouse gases such as carbon dioxide, methane and nitrous oxide have caused much of the observed increase in Earth's temperatures over the past 50 years^[4].

2.0 Objective

Among the most known processes conversion of CO₂ to other useful materials can be done following routes in photocatalysis, radiochemistry, thermochemistry, biochemistry and electrolysis. Our process has undertaken the electrolytic route due to the following advantages:

- Selectivity of product produced at each electrode
- The tools and materials used are fairly simple as they do not require the creation of high vacuum and high temperature conditions.

2.1 The main objective of our experiment is to reduce dependence on fossil fuel besides controlling most of the emission problems faced by steel industries. Ethanol and its by products are of immense use to mankind as it has manifold uses as fuel, cleaning agents, beverages and aerosols. As the main output of our process is ethanol we establish the main aim of our project as “ Waste to Energy “.

2.2 As the new sellable product ethanol has potential to bring more revenues to the industry which may be used for maintenance of the conversion plant itself. However setting up a separate R&D unit for the conversion mechanism may not be a good investment to make when we can involve methods of artificial intelligence to make the conversion process more robust. The second part of our project aims at minimizing human role in controlling the activities of the conversion unit as it proposes an auto feedback system which returns instruction on how to run the plant with better efficiency. This is a small step toward the goal of achieving a fully autonomous system for conversion plant control.

3.0 Methodology

Setting Up of Apparatus.

3.1 Instruments Used:

1. Laboratory Tube furnace
2. Electrical suction pump
3. PVC pipes and attachments
4. Two-way valve
5. Round Bottomed Flask
6. Glass beaker
7. Arduino Uno
8. Bread board
9. MQ 135 sensor
10. Male/Female wires
11. Mild steel bar

3.2 Chemicals Used

1. Charcoal (Activated)
2. Hematite (Fe_2O_3)
3. Boric Acid
4. Nickel Sulphate
5. Nickel Chloride
6. Zinc Dust
7. Hydrochloric acid

3.3 Cell Design and related processes:

Electrodes

Cathode- Nickel plated mild steel

Anode- Graphite

Electrolyte- Water

Gases- CO_2 (IN and OUT), Water Vapor

Cell Reactions:

Overall cell reaction: $4\text{CO}_2 + 6\text{H}_2\text{O} + 2\text{H}_2 \longrightarrow 2\text{CH}_3\text{CH}_2\text{OH} + 5\text{O}_2$

Anodic Reaction: $2\text{H}_2 \longrightarrow 4\text{H}^+ + 4\text{e}^-$

Cathodic Reaction: $4\text{CO}_2 + 6\text{H}_2\text{O} + 4\text{e}^- \longrightarrow 2\text{CH}_3\text{CH}_2\text{OH} + 5\text{O}_2 + 2\text{OH}^-$

3.4 Nickel plating of Mild Steel bar

Chemicals used: Nickel sulfate (NiSO_4), Nickel Chloride (NiCl_2) and Boric Acid (H_3BO_3)

Cathode: Mild steel bar

Anode: Graphite rod

Electrolyte: Aqueous solution of 5.9 g NiCl_2 , 3.5g NiSO_4 , 1.5g H_3BO_3

Current applied: 1mA per cm^2 of mild steel plate

Procedure: 5.9 g NiCl_2 , 3.5g NiSO_4 , 1.5g H_3BO_3 was mixed with 100ml water and stirred until the solution turns green. Then it was heated to 80°C for two minutes and stirred again. A mild steel bar was cleared from all scales and rust with a mechanical belt abrasion machine. 2.5cm^2 of the bar was exposed after wrapping the remaining area with teflon tape and immersed into the solution. 2.5mA of electric current was applied.

Result: Nickel plated mild steel bar was produced. This Nickel-plated mild steel electrode is later used as the cathode in the main conversion cell.

3.5 Hydrogen synthesis unit

Chemicals used: Zn dust and conc. HCl

Procedure: concentrated HCl was diluted by slowly pouring it down the side of a beaker containing water. Once diluted the acid is made to fall dropwise into a conical flask containing Zn dust. Violent reaction ensued with H_2 gas generation.

The evolved hydrogen gas is fed directly into the cell by a pipe.

3.6 Furnace Unit

A laboratory tube furnace was used for the experiments. The furnace is controlled with an electrical thermocouple controller. Both ends of the tube were sealed with a cork during the process barring the outlet pipe to carry the exhaust gases. An air pump evacuates the gas from the furnace and feeds into the cell through a two - way valve. The reactions inside the furnace are:

Overall reaction:

3.7 Gas flow control unit

At the entrance of the gas pipe to the cell the gas flows through a two-way valve to control the input and output of gas to the cell. This also controls whether the inflow or the outflow gases pass through the MQ135 sensors. We wish to make this valve servo operated for the autonomous machine.

3.8 Electronics Control unit and Data acquisition

The MQ135 sensor collects CO₂ data which is processed with an Arduino Uno processor and is fed into the attached control computer through optical fiber cables. Also, the processor transfers data to a remote device through a booth module.

Photograph 1 Sealed tube f/c

Photograph 2 Arduino circuitry

Photograph 3 Two-way valve

3.9 Overall Setup Description

Photograph 4 shows the experimental setup at Extractive Metallurgy laboratory at Metallurgical and Material Engineering department at Jadavpur University. The photo was taken in 2019

The photograph shows the Tube furnace, Robotic circuitry system, the data acquisition system connected.

4.0 Results and Discussion

4.1 Experiment 1:

Condition: 648°C through 700°C

Procedure: Readings were taken from the gas out flow nozzle of the cell in intervals of 5 seconds for 5 minutes.

Observation:

- ❑ The highest yield of Ethanol observed was 493ppm at 105 sec after the beginning when unused CO and CO₂ were 16 ppm and 3046 ppm respectively.
- ❑ 493ppm yield repeated once again at 120 sec after beginning when unused CO and CO₂ were 45 ppm and 3205 ppm respectively.

Figure 2 shows the exhaust analysis of experiment 1

4.2 Experiment 2:

Condition: 700°C through 750°C

Procedure: Readings were taken from the gas out flow nozzle of the cell in intervals of 5 seconds for 8 minutes.

Observation:

- ❑ The highest yield of Ethanol observed was 497ppm at 420 sec after the beginning when unused CO and CO₂ were 26 ppm and 2406 ppm respectively.

Figure 3 shows exhaust analysis of experiment 2

4.3 Experiment 3:

Condition: 650°C through 700°C with Hematite reduction.

Procedure: Readings were taken from the gas out flow nozzle of the cell in intervals of 5 seconds for 4 minutes.

Observation:

- ❑ The highest yield of Ethanol observed was 323ppm at 55 sec after the beginning when unused CO and CO₂ were 55 ppm and 3205 ppm respectively.
- ❑ Lower yield was observed after than last experiments.

Figure 4 shows the exhaust analysis of experiment 3

4.4 Experiment 4

Condition: 700°C through 750°C with Hematite reduction.

Procedure: Readings were taken from the gas out flow nozzle of the cell in intervals of 5 seconds for 8 minutes.

Observation:

- The highest yield of Ethanol observed was 248ppm at 375 sec after the beginning when unused CO and CO₂ were 23 ppm and 2805 ppm respectively.
- Lower yield was observed after than experiments 1 and 2

4.5 Experiment 5 (Long Duration)

Condition: 650°C through 760°C with Hematite reduction.

Procedure: Readings were taken from the gas out flow nozzle of the cell in intervals of 5 seconds for 17 minutes.

Observation:

- The highest yield of Ethanol observed was 247ppm at 765 sec after the beginning when unused CO and CO₂ were 27 ppm and 3317 ppm respectively.
- Lower yield was observed than experiments 1 and 2.

5.0 Simulations using the method of Gradient descent

It can be observed that the data fluctuations in the logarithmic graphs are much reduced as compared to the linear graphs.

In Fig. 1 the range of fluctuations in the order of 4.5×10^3 has been reduced to 3.5×10^3 .

Therefore, log of the values reduces the possibility of overfitting in the data besides decreasing convergence time of the cost function reducing the need for feature scaling of the data and mean normalization.

5.1 Theory of Gradient Descent:

5.1.1 Supervised learning:

In supervised learning, we are given a data set and already know what our correct output should look like, having the idea that there is a relationship between the input and the output.

Supervised learning problems are categorized into "regression" and "classification" problems. In a regression problem, we are trying to predict results within a continuous output, meaning that we are trying to map input variables to some continuous function.

Regression - Given a picture of a person, we have to predict their age on the basis of the given picture

Training set: This consists of a set of values of the function and their arguments which serve as a database where the program is trained. A list of m training examples $(x^{(i)}, y^{(i)})$ where $i = 1, 2, \dots, m-1, m$ is called the training set. $X=Y=R$.

The goal of the program is to learn a real function h such that $h: X \rightarrow Y$ so that $h(x)$ is a good predictor of the corresponding value of y . Initially h is called a hypothesis which is improvised with iterations.

$$h_{\theta}(x) = \theta_0 + \theta_1 x^{(1)} + \dots + \theta_{n+1} x^{(n+1)} + \theta_n x^{(n)}$$

5.1.2 Cost function:

The cost function measures the accuracy of the hypothesis. It is actually similar to the average of the difference between the predicted results of all the hypotheses with inputs from X and outputs in Y with the actual Y data.

$$J(\theta_0, \theta_1, \dots, \theta_n) = \frac{1}{2m} \sum_{i=1}^m (h_{\theta}(x_i) - y_i)^2$$

Mathematically it is the mean squared error.

5.1.3 Gradient Descent^[8]:

In order to minimize the values of $\theta_0, \theta_1, \dots, \theta_{n+1}, \theta_n$ i.e minimize the value of difference $|h_{\theta}(x_i) - y_i|$, we follow the method of gradient descent.

For $\theta_j : j=0, 1, \dots, n-1, n$

$$\theta_j := \theta_j - \alpha \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta_j} J(\theta_0, \theta_1, \dots, \theta_n) \text{ in each iteration.}$$

The simultaneous update of all the θ values in each iteration done and the value of the cost function is evaluated. The α value is input such that $J(\theta_0, \theta_1, \dots, \theta_n)$ value converges i.e. becomes constant. A bigger α value might result in the hypothesis failing to converge i.e. the value of the cost function becoming positive.

$$\theta_j := \theta_j - \alpha \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta_j} J(\theta_0, \theta_1, \dots, \theta_n) \Rightarrow \theta_j := \theta_j - \alpha \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m (h_{\theta}(x_i) - y_i) x_i$$

6.1 Result and Discussion

Software used: GNU Octave 5.2.0 Copyright © John W. Eaton and others

Device used : mayukh@MayukhsMacBook-Pro

Program used: Sourcecode.m

Functions used: gradientDescent1.m, computeCost.m and predictor.m.

6.2 Process: The data is converted to a 1000X3 matrix and the log of the values are taken. Sourcecode.m takes the logged values as input and computes the equation to predict ethanol output given the values of CO, CO₂ input.

6.3 Experiment 6

Parameters: Number of iterations : 1000, Value of coefficient of gradient descent α : 0.01

INPUT

Hypothesis: $h_{\theta}(x) = \theta_0 + \theta_1 \log \text{CO} + \theta_2 \log \text{CO}_2$
where $\theta_0 = \theta_1 = \theta_2 = 0$

Output:

$\theta_0 = 0.159844$

$\theta_1 = 0.119728$

$\theta_2 = 0.590693$

```
0.025333
0.025332
0.025331
0.025330
0.025329
0.025329
0.025328
0.025327
0.025326
0.025325
0.025324
0.025323
0.025323
0.025322
0.025321
0.025320
Theta values :
0.159844
0.119728
0.590693
THE FINAL MODEL EQUATION IS:
Expected log Ethanol output=0.159844 + (0.119728)log CO. + (0.590693)log CO2
octave:4>
```

Figure 12 shows the output of Experiment 6

Final equation: $h_{\theta}(x) = 0.159844 + (0.119728) \log \text{CO} + (0.590693) \log \text{CO}_2$

Figure 13 shows data points i.e. values of Ethanol concentration (red crosses) and the equation's estimation (blue lines) for Experiment 6

6.4 Experiment 7

Parameters: Number of iterations : 10000, Value of coefficient of gradient descent α : 0.01

INPUT

Hypothesis: $h_{\theta}(x) = \theta_0 + \theta_1 \log CO + \theta_2 \log CO_2$ where $\theta_0 = \theta_1 = \theta_2 = 0$

Output:

$$\theta_0 = 0.907626$$

$$\theta_1 = 0.097126$$

$$\theta_2 = 0.510046$$

Final equation: $h_{\theta}(x) = 0.907626 + (0.097126)\log CO + (0.510046)\log CO_2$

```

0.019019
0.019019
0.019018
0.019017
0.019017
0.019016
0.019016
0.019015
0.019014
0.019014
0.019013
0.019013
0.019012
0.019011
0.019011
0.019010
Theta values :
0.907626
0.097126
0.510049
THE FINAL MODEL EQUATION IS:
Expected log Ethanol output=0.907626 + (0.097126)log CO. + (0.510049)log CO2
octave:5>

```

Figure 14 shows the output of Experiment 7

Figure 17 shows data points i.e. values of Ethanol concentration (red crosses) and the equation's estimation (blue lines) for Experiment 8

6.6 Observation of Experiments 6 through 8

- It can be observed that least deviation of the function is in Experiment 8.

Due to the larger number of iterations and constant coefficient of gradient descent the degree of bias is the least.

- The predictions of the equations with iterations 1000 and 10000 are comparatively inaccurate as they show larger deviation i.e. the function has more tendency to bend and pass through most points. As most of these points have some degree of error the equation passing

through them are no-doubt erroneous.

The closest approximation to a linear function is given by Experiment 8.

Greater than 100000 iterations is limited by the computational ability of the device used.

Figure 18 shows the cost function achieving its minimum value and becoming constant.

6.7 Inference

Therefore,

$\log \text{Ethanol output} = 4.468770 + (0.021503)\log \text{CO} + (0.113081)\log \text{CO}_2$
is the final predicted equation.

7.0 Discussion

1. For our experiment we had analyzed the gas out flow from the cell. Carbon dioxide influx can also be considered as a parameter for the machine learning process for greater accuracy.
2. Our readings were taken with furnace temperatures between 648 °C to 800 °C. Temperature zones greater than 800 °C need to be studied.
3. The experiment was done in two days with three furnace runs. A continuous furnace run may have been brought data of similar nature.
4. In the last part of the project we had trained a program to compute the out put of ethanol based on the accompanying gas quantities. This gives the operator an estimate of the out put and gives him the upper hand in controlling the process.
5. Other parameters like humidity, furnace temperature, Voltage applied to the cell, Gas input values besides the output values could be considered as parameters for the training set.
6. An autonomous system can be easily designed which can maintain its efficiency on its own based on the supervised learning process.
7. The Carbon dioxide output can be refed into the same cell or be fed in a series of many cells connected. This will reduce its emission to the atmosphere to zero.
8. Ethanol synthesized by our process can be used as a fuel for the steel industry itself. Besides it fetches high market value as a consumable item as well as for medical purposes. This has potential to bring high revenues to the industry and may be conducive for its sustainability.
9. Our project is a mammoth step towards achieving the “Greener Tomorrow” in Industry 4.0

7.1 Reasons for incomplete work and new direction of project:

Previously we had planned for at least ten furnace runs but we were able to complete only two furnace runs. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic situation and the lockdown that ensued from 25th March the later part of the experiments had remained undone. To make good utilization of the time we had conducted extensive study and even learning a few concepts of Machine Learning that could find some application here. Thereby we conducted extensive tests on various regression analysis programs to find a good fit of the data to an equation. We would consider ourselves fortunate as the time we gained due to this lock

down has given us an opportunity to explore a new direction of the project. Involving concepts of Machine learning and AI is need of today as the industries are aiming for better production efficiency and profits besides dodging the sanctions put forward by various governments to curb polluting industries.

Another reason for our incomplete work is that our approach was very less calculated. For instance often the hydrogen inflow into the cell stopped before all data was taken due to lesser quantity of the acid dropping over Zn powder. The temperature rise rate of the furnace is quite moderate and as a result of it often hydrogen supply runs out from the cell. A more calculated approach with fluid flux meter and electronic control valves might have yielded better data for a longer direction. To simulate an Ideal case hydrogen supply from a tank would have been much efficient.

There have been various leakages from the tube furnace. The two ends of the tube was sealed with cork and foam. Due to smaller size of the cork and similar steric incompatibility there must have been various leakages in exhaust leakage despite the suction pump.

The above mentioned reasons resulted in incomplete and incomparable data which clubbed with the sudden abortion of experiments due to the pandemic situation is the reason of our partially complete project work.

8.0 Reference

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7. "Cycles and Trends in solar irradiance and climate" by Judith Lean, Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Climate Change, vol. 1, January/February 2010, 111-122
8. "Machine Learning" by Andrew Ng, Stanford University

9.0 Appendix

9.1 Arduino code:

```
#include <SoftwareSerial.h>
#include <dht.h>
#include <MQ135.h>
#include <Wire.h>
```

```
SoftwareSerial BTserial(10, 11); // TX | RX
int led = 13;
int led2 = 12;
```

```
//int sensorPin = A0;
int Analog_Input = A1;
int CO,CO2, NH3, Ethanol, Toluene, Acetone;
```

```
//int sensorValue = 0;
//int sensorValue1 = 0;
```

```
//dht DHT;
//#define DHT11_PIN A0
```

```
MQ135 mq135(Analog_Input);
```

```
void setup()
{
  Serial.begin(9600);
  BTserial.begin(9600);
  pinMode(led, OUTPUT);
  digitalWrite(led, HIGH);
  pinMode(led2, OUTPUT);
  digitalWrite(led2, HIGH);
```

```
  // mq135.begin();
  Serial.println( " Project Conversion of Exhaust CO2 gas to Alcohol for Sustainable Green Process of
  IronMaking ");
  Serial.println( " By Mayukh Das and Shailesh Kumar, Dept of Met & Mat Engg, JU kolkata ");

  Serial.println( " CO CO2 Ethanol");
```

```

}

void loop() {

/*int chk = DHT.read11(DHT11_PIN);
sensorValue = analogRead(sensorPin);// Read A0
sensorValue1 = analogRead(sensorPin);// Read A0

sensorValue1= 2.5*DHT.humidity;
sensorValue= DHT.temperature; */

//float* values= mq135.read(true);

CO = mq135.getCOPPM(); if(CO<0) CO=0;

CO2 = mq135.getCO2PPM(); if(CO2<0) CO2=0;
if (CO2>8000)
digitalWrite(led, HIGH);
else digitalWrite(led,LOW);

Ethanol=mq135.getEthanolPPM(); if(Ethanol<0) Ethanol=0;
if ( Ethanol>500)
{ digitalWrite(led2, HIGH);
Serial.println(" Ethanol Detected Good");
}
else { digitalWrite(led2,LOW);
Serial.println(" Ethanol Not Detected , not achieved");}
/*NH3 = mq135.getNH4PPM(); if(NH3<0) NH3=0;

Acetone=mq135.getAcetonePPM(); if(Acetone<0) Acetone=0;

Toluene=mq135.getToluenePPM(); if(Toluene<0) Toluene=0;*/
Serial.print(" ");
Serial.print(CO);
Serial.print(" ");
Serial.print(CO2);
Serial.print(" ");
Serial.print(Ethanol);
Serial.println(" ");
/* Serial.print(NH3);
Serial.print(" ");

```

```
Serial.print(Acetone);  
Serial.print( "  ");  
Serial.print(Toluene);  
Serial.print( "  ");  
Serial.print(sensorValue1);  
Serial.print( "  ");  
Serial.println(sensorValue); */
```

//IMPORTANT: The complete String has to be of the Form: 1234,1234,1234,1234;

//(every Value has to be seperated through a comma (',') and the message has to

//end with a semikolon (';'))

```
BTserial.print(CO);
```

```
BTserial.print(",");
```

```
BTserial.print(CO2);
```

```
/*BTserial.print(",");
```

```
BTserial.print(NH3);
```

```
BTserial.print(",");
```

```
BTserial.print(Ethanol);
```

```
BTserial.print(",");
```

```
BTserial.print(Acetone);
```

```
BTserial.print(",");
```

```
BTserial.print(Toluene);
```

```
BTserial.print(",");
```

```
BTserial.print(sensorValue1);
```

```

BTserial.print(",");

BTserial.print(sensorValue); */
BTserial.print(";");

//message to the receiving device

delay(5000);

}

```

9.2 Code for converting absolute data to logarithmic data in GNU Octave

```

octave:2> cd /Users/mayukh/Documents/EthCObar
octave:3> pwd
ans = /Users/mayukh/Documents/EthCObar
octave:4> beta=load('Data1.txt');
octave:5> alpha=[ (log(beta(:,1))) (log(beta(:,2))) (log(beta(:,3))))];
octave:6> save logdata.txt alpha

```

9.3 Source Code:

```

%Ethanol to Carbondioxide conversion model. Following linear regression
data=load('logdata.txt');
Y=data(:,1);
l=length(data);
X=[ones(l,1) data(:,2) data(:,3)];
theta=zeros(3,1);
iterations=100000;
alpha=0.01;
dat1=zeros(iterations,2);
computeCost(X,Y,theta);
counter = zeros(iterations, 1);
for iter = 1:iterations
counter(iter) = [iter];
end

```

```

history= gradientDescent1(X, Y, theta, alpha, iterations);
dat1=[history];
fprintf('Cost function values :\n');
fprintf('%f\n',dat1);
%-----Cost function minimization graph-----
plot(counter,dat1);
xlabel('Iterations');
ylabel('Cost function');
%-----Theta values-----
theta= gradientDescent2(X, Y, theta, alpha, iterations);
fprintf('Theta values :\n');
fprintf('%f\n',theta);
%-----Model equation-----
fprintf('THE FINAL MODEL EQUATION IS:\n')
fprintf('Expected log Ethanol output=')
fprintf('%f',theta(1,:))
fprintf(' + ')
fprintf('(')
fprintf('%f',theta(2,:))
fprintf(')')
fprintf('log CO.')
fprintf(' + ')
fprintf('(')
fprintf('%f',theta(3,:))
fprintf(')')
fprintf('log CO2 \n')
%fprintf('+')
%fprintf('%f',theta(4,:))
%fprintf(' Furnace temperature.\n')
%-----Result comparison of model with data-----
prediction=predictor(theta,X);
for pt = 1:l
number(pt) = [pt];
end

plot(number, prediction);
hold on;
plot(number, Y, 'rx', 'Markersize', 10);
xlabel('Datapoints');
ylabel('Values');

```

9.4 Compute Cost:

```
function J = computeCost(X, Y, theta)
%COMPUTECOST Compute cost for linear regression
% J = COMPUTECOST(X, Y, theta) computes the cost of using theta as the
% parameter for linear regression to fit the data points in X and y

% Initialize some useful values
m = length(Y); % number of training examples

% You need to return the following variables correctly
A=((theta)')*X'-Y';
B=A.^2;
J = (1/(2*m))*(sum(B',1));

End
```

9.5 Gradient descent:

```
function [history] = gradientDescent1(X, Y, theta, alpha, num_iters)
m = length(Y); % number of training examples
cost = zeros(num_iters, 1);

for iter = 1:num_iters
A=((theta)')*X'-Y';
B=A*X;
delta = (1/(m))*B';
theta=theta-(alpha)*delta;

% Save the cost J in every iteration
cost(iter) = [computeCost(X, Y, theta)];

end
history=[cost];
End
```

9.6 Predictor:

```
function[prediction]=predictor(theta,X)
C=((theta)')*X';
D=C';
prediction=D;
end
```

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-----*End*-----